

Research Article

Development and validation of first order derivative spectroscopy method for simultaneous estimation of candesartan cilexetil and pioglitazone hydrochloride in synthetic mixture

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ABSTRACT

Objective: Objective of the study was to develop a simple, accurate, precise, economic, robust and rugged UV spectrophotometric method and validate for the simultaneous estimation of Candesartan Cilexetil and Pioglitazone Hydrochloride in synthetic mixture.

Methods: Combination of Candesartan Cilexetil and Pioglitazone Hydrochloride has only one LC-MS/MS analytical method developed yet, so this UV method was novel for combined synthetic dosage of Candesartan Cilexetil and Pioglitazone Hydrochloride (1:2). This method utilizes methanol as a solvent. Zero crossing point (ZCP) of Candesartan Cilexetil and Pioglitazone hydrochloride were found to be 242.00 nm and 327.60 nm respectively. Hence, estimation of Candesartan Cilexetil and Pioglitazone Hydrochloride were done at 327.60 nm and 242.00 nm respectively.

Results: The linearity of Candesartan Cilexetil and Pioglitazone Hydrochloride were found to be in range 10-50 µg/ml and 20-100 µg/ml ($R^2=0.9995$) respectively. The accuracy of the present method was evaluated at 80%, 100% and 120%. Recovery was found to be in range 99.50-100.80% and 99.27%-101.36% for Candesartan Cilexetil and Pioglitazone Hydrochloride respectively. Intermediate precision studies were carried out and the RSD values were less than one. The value of LOD and LOQ were found to be 0.170 and 0.516 µg/ml for Candesartan Cilexetil and 0.207 and 0.625 µg/ml for Pioglitazone Hydrochloride.

Conclusions: It can be concluded from the results that the proposed method was sensitive, accurate, precise and reproducible for the simultaneous determination of Candesartan Cilexetil and Pioglitazone Hydrochloride in Synthetic Mixture.

Keywords: Candesartan Cilexetil, Development, Pioglitazone Hydrochloride, Derivative, Validation

Introduction

The present study was aimed to develop simple, Accurate, precise and sensitive analytical method for simultaneous estimation of Candesartan Cilexetil (CAN) and Pioglitazone Hydrochloride (PIO). Candesartan Cilexetil, an angiotensin II receptor antagonist is used mainly for the treatment of Hypertension. Candesartan Cilexetil is the prodrug of Candesartan, an angiotensin II receptor antagonist. Candesartan binds selectively and non-competitively to the angiotensin II receptor type 1, thus preventing the actions of angiotensin II.¹ It have been widely used in treatment of diseases like hypertension, heart failure, myocardial infarction and diabetic nephropathy. IUPAC name of Candesartan Cilexetil is (1RS)-1-(cyclohexyloxy carbonyloxy) ethyl-2-ethoxy-1-{{2'-(1H-tetrazol-5-yl)biphenyl-4-yl}methyl}-1H-benzo[d]imidazole-7-carboxylate.²

Figure 1: Structure of Candesartan Cilexetil.²

Candesartan Cilexetil is white or almost white, crystalline powder. Solubility is given in practically insoluble in water, sparingly soluble in methanol, Highly Soluble in dimethyl sulfoxide or 1N Sodium carbonate solution, ethanol, acetonitrile.

Pioglitazone Hydrochloride is used for the treatment of diabetes mellitus type 2. Pioglitazone acts as an agonist at peroxisome proliferator activated receptors (PPAR) in target tissues for insulin action such as adipose tissue, skeletal muscle, and liver. Activation of PPAR-gamma receptors increases the transcription of insulin-responsive genes involved in the control of glucose production, transport, and utilization. In this way, pioglitazone both enhances tissue

sensitivity to insulin and reduces hepatic gluconeogenesis. Thus, insulin resistance associated with type 2 diabetes mellitus is improved without an increase in insulin secretion by pancreatic β cells.³

The chemical name is (5RS)-5-{4-[2-(5-Ethylpyridin-2-yl) ethoxy]benzyl}thiazolidine-2,4-dione monoHydrochloride. Pioglitazone hydrochloride is a white or almost White solid crystalline powder that is Practically insoluble in water, Soluble in methanol, N,N-dimethylformamide and Slightly soluble in ethanol.²

Figure 2: Structure of Pioglitazone Hydrochloride.²

Combination of Candesartan Cilexetil and Pioglitazone Hydrochloride therapy specially in Metabolic syndrome. Candesartan Cilexetil in combination with Pioglitazone Hydrochloride has been proved to provide beneficial effect (synergistic effect) in metabolic syndrome, anti-inflammatory and enhanced organ protective effects.⁴

The review of literature regarding quantitative analysis of Candesartan Cilexetil and Pioglitazone Hydrochloride revealed that only LC-MS/MS Analytical method was developed in combination. Some spectrometric methods and chromatographic methods have been reported for the estimation of the individual drugs. The focus of the present study was to develop and validate a Simple, Accurate and Precise First Order Derivative method for the estimation of Candesartan Cilexetil and Pioglitazone Hydrochloride in Synthetic mixture.

Materials and Methods

Instrumentation

A double beam UV/Visible spectrophotometer (Shimadzu model 2450, Japan) with spectral width of 2 nm, 1 cm quartz cells was used to measure absorbance of all the solutions. Spectra were automatically obtained by UV-Probe system software. An analytical balance (Sartorius CD 2250, Germany) was used for weighing the samples. Sonicator (D120/2H, TRANS-O-SONIC). All instruments and glasswares were calibrated.

Material and reagents

Candesartan Cilexetil raw material was received as gift sample from CTX Life science, Surat. Pioglitazone Hydrochloride raw material was received as gift sample from Cadila Healthcare, Ankleshwar. Methanol AR Grade (FINAR), Distilled Water, NaOH AR Grade (RANCHEM), Hcl (ASTRON) was used for development purpose.

Table 1: Composition of synthetic mixture.

Candesartan Cilexetil	8 mg
Pioglitazone Hydrochloride	16.53 mg
D- Mannitol	83.7 mg
Hydroxy Propyl Methyl Cellulose (HPMC-2910)	3.25 mg
Crytalline Cellulose	52 mg
Magnesium Stearate	q.s.
Talc	q.s.
TOTAL	200 mg

Preparation of standard stock solution of Candesartan Cilexetil and Pioglitazone Hydrochloride

Accurately weighed quantity 100 mg of CAN and PIO were transferred into separate 100 ml volumetric flask, dissolved and diluted up to mark with methanol (100 ml). This will give a stock solution having strength of 1000 µg/ml of each.

Preparation of working standard solution of Candesartan Cilexetil and Pioglitazone Hydrochloride

From the Standard stock solution (1000 µg/ml) for both drugs, Suitable aliquots of this solution were diluted up to the mark with methanol to get the concentration range of 10, 20, 30, 40 and 50 µg/ml for CAN and 20, 40, 60, 80 and 100 for PIO.

Selection of analytical wavelength

From standard stock solution of CAN (1000 µg/ml) and PIO (100 µg/ml), 10 µg/ml for CAN and 20 µg/ml for PIO were prepared respectively and each solution was scanned between 200-400 nm. The first order derivative spectra of each solution were obtained. First order derivative spectrum for CAN showed zero crossing point at 242.00 nm. The wavelength selected for estimation of CAN was 327.60 nm (ZCP of PIO) because it showed adequate absorbance at this wavelength in mixture. First order derivative spectrum for PIO showed zero crossing point at 327.60 nm. The wavelength selected for estimation of PIO was 242.00 nm (ZCP of CAN) because it showed adequate absorbance at this wavelength in mixture (Figure 3 and 4).

Preparation of calibration curve

Standard solutions of CAN in the concentration range of 10 to 50 µg/ml obtained by transferring (0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4 and 0.5 ml) of CAN stock solution (1000 µg/ml) to the series of 10 ml volumetric flasks and standard solutions of PIO in the concentration range of 20 to 100 µg/ml were obtained by transferring (0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8 and 1.0 ml) of PIO stock solution (1000 µg/ml) to the series of 10 ml volumetric flasks. Then volume was adjusted up-to mark with methanol. Absorbance of each solution for CAN was measured at 327.60 nm using first order derivative spectrophotometry and absorbance of each solution for PIO was measured at 242.00 nm using first order derivative spectrophotometry. The graph of absorbance vs. respective concentration was plotted.

Analytical method validation⁶

The method was validated as per ICH guidelines. The objective of validation of an analytical procedure was to demonstrate whether the procedure was suitable for its intended purpose. The proposed method was validated for various parameters such as linearity and range, precision, limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantitation (LOQ) and accuracy according to ICH Q2 (R1) guideline.

Linearity

The linearity of the method was determined at concentration levels ranging from 10-50 µg/ml for Candesartan Cilexetil and 20-100 µg/ml for Pioglitazone Hydrochloride shown in Figure 4. The calibration curve was constructed by plotting response factor against concentration of drugs shown in Figure 5 and 6.

Correlation coefficient (r^2) for calibration curve of CAN and PIO was found to be 0.9995 and 0.9994, respectively.

The regression line equation for CAN and PIO are as following,

$$y = -0.010x - 0.062 \text{ for CAN } \underline{\hspace{2cm}} \quad (1)$$

$$y = -0.036x - 0.219 \text{ for PIO } \underline{\hspace{2cm}} \quad (2)$$

Precision

The precision of the method was demonstrated by interday and intraday variation studies. In the intraday studies, three different concentrations of standard solutions were made and the response factor of drug concentration and percentage RSD were calculated. In the inter day variation studies, three different concentration of standard solutions were made for three consecutive days and response factor of drug concentration and percentage RSD were calculated and are reported in Table 3 and 4.

Accuracy

The accuracy of the method was determined by recovery experiments. The recovery studies were carried out in three levels such as 80%, 100% and 120%. The percentage recoveries were calculated and are presented in Table 5 and

6, for Candesartan Cilexetil and Pioglitazone Hydrochloride respectively. The value of %Recovery within the limit indicated that the method is accurate and percentage recovery shows that there is no interference from the excipients.

Limit of detection and quantitation

Calibration method

Five sets of known concentrations (10-50 µg/ml) for Candesartan Cilexetil and (20-100 µg/ml) were prepared. Calibration curves were plotted for each set. LOD and LOQ were calculated using the regression equation and following formulae as shown below and reported in Table 7.

$$\text{LOD} = 3.3 * \text{SD/S}$$

$$\text{LOQ} = 10 * \text{SD/S}$$

Where, SD is standard deviation of y-intercept of the calibration curves and S is mean slope of six calibration curves.

Robustness and ruggedness

Robustness and Ruggedness of the method was determined by creating variations in Instrument, Analyst, Solvent Change and Synthetic mixture ratio and determining %RSD. Data is reported in Table 8.

Assay

The proposed method was applied to the simultaneous estimation of Candesartan Cilexetil and Pioglitazone Hydrochloride in Synthetic Mixture. A first order spectrum of the sample solution containing 20 µg/ml of CAN and 40 µg/ml of PIO was recorded and the absorbance at 327.60 nm and 242.00 nm were noted for estimation of CAN and PIO, respectively.

The concentration of CAN and PIO in mixture was determined using the corresponding calibration graph. The results from the analysis of synthetic mixture containing Candesartan Cilexetil (20 µg/ml) and Pioglitazone Hydrochloride (40 µg/ml) in combination are presented in Table in 9.

The percentage assay shows that there is no interference from excipients and the proposed method can successfully applied to analysis of commercial formulation containing CAN and PIO. The % assay values are tabulated in Table 9.

Results and Discussion

Table 2: Calibration data for CAN and PIO *(n=6).

Sr. No	Concentration (µg/ml)		Absorbance* (327.60 nm) ± SD	Absorbance* (242.0 nm) ± SD
	CAN	PIO	CAN	SD
1	10	20	-0.1690 ± 0.0014	-0.9180 ± 0.0031
2	20	40	-0.2650 ± 0.0018	-1.7610 ± 0.0062
3	30	60	-0.3840 ± 0.0017	-2.4230 ± 0.0051
4	40	80	-0.4830 ± 0.0019	-3.1545 ± 0.0103
5	50	100	-0.5880 ± 0.0019	-3.9126 ± 0.0075

An attempt was made to develop an accurate, precise and reproducible first order derivative

spectroscopy method for the simultaneous determination of Candesartan Cilexetil and Pioglitazone Hydrochloride in Synthetic Mixture.

Figure 3: Overlain first order spectra of CAN and PIO in 1:2 ratio with mixture.

Figure 4: Overlain first order spectra of CAN and PIO in 1:2 ratio, respectively.

Table 3: Intraday precision data for estimation of CAN and PIO *(n=3).

Conc. (µg/ml)		Abs.* (CAN) Avg. ± SD (327.60 nm)	% RSD	Abs.* (PIO) Avg. ± SD (242.00 nm)	% RSD
CAN	PIO				
10	20	-0.1623 ± 0.0006	0.355	-1.0130 ± 0.0052	0.512
30	60	-0.3640 ± 0.0010	0.274	-2.4070 ± 0.0070	0.291
50	100	-0.5800 ± 0.0010	0.172	-3.6870 ± 0.0061	0.165

Table 4: Interday precision data for estimation of CAN and PIO *(n=3).

Conc. (µg/ml)		Abs.* (CAN) Avg. ± SD (327.60 nm)	% RSD	Abs.* (PIO) Avg. ± SD (242.00 nm)	% RSD
CAN	PIO				
10	20	-0.1620 ± 0.0010	0.617	-1.0086 ± 0.0025	0.249
30	60	-0.3636 ± 0.0015	0.420	-2.4026 ± 0.0118	0.493
50	100	-0.5813 ± 0.0015	0.263	-3.6860 ± 0.0113	0.306

Table 5: Recovery data of CAN *(n=3).

Concentration of CAN from formulation (mg)	Concentration of Std. CAN added (mg)	Total Concentration of CAN (µg/ml)	Total amount of CAN found (µg/ml) Mean* ± SD	% Recovery (n=3)
20	-	20	19.90 ± 0.100	99.50
20	16	36	35.86 ± 0.264	99.75
20	20	40	40.06 ± 0.153	100.80
20	24	44	43.93 ± 0.153	100.12

Table 6: Recovery data of PIO *(n=3).

Concentration of PIO from formulation (mg)	Concentration of Std. PIO added (mg)	Total Concentration of PIO (µg/ml)	Total amount of PIO found (µg/ml) Mean* ± SD	% Recovery (n=3)
40	-	40	40.54 ± 0.227	101.36
40	32	72	72.32 ± 0.070	99.31
40	40	80	80.25 ± 0.192	99.27
40	48	88	88.32 ± 0.112	99.54

Table 7: LOD and LOQ data of CAN and PIO*(n=10).

Conc. (µg/ml)		Avg. ± SD (327.60 nm)* CAN	% RSD	Avg. ± SD (242.00 nm) PIO	% RSD
CAN	PIO				
10	20	-0.1606 ± 0.0005	0.321	-1.0057 ± 0.0022	0.225
LOD (µg/ml)		0.170		0.207	
LOQ (µg/ml)		0.516		0.628	

Table 8: Robustness and ruggedness data of CAN and PIO *(n=3).

Robustness data of Candesartan Cilexetil (10 µg/ml) and Pioglitazone Hydrochloride (20 µg/ml) (n=3)*						
No	Factor	Level	CAN Abs.* ± SD	%RSD	PIO Abs.* ± SD	%RSD
1.	Change in Instrument	UV-2450	-0.161 ± 0.0010	0.621	-1.013 ± 0.0051	0.513
		UV-1800	-0.162 ± 0.0010	0.617	-1.011 ± 0.0011	0.114
2.	Change in Analyst	Analyst-1	-0.162 ± 0.0011	0.617	-1.012 ± 0.0034	0.342
		Analyst-2	-0.161 ± 0.0015	0.946	-1.011 ± 0.0029	0.285
Ruggedness data of Candesartan Cilexetil and Pioglitazone Hydrochloride (n=3)*						
3.	Change in solvent	90 % Methanol	-0.336 ± 0.0010	0.297	-1.530 ± 0.0100	0.653
		10 % Methanol	-0.303 ± 0.0015	0.503	-0.751 ± 0.0010	0.133
4.	Change mixture ratio (CAN+PIO)	3:1	-0.951 ± 0.0010	0.105	-0.156 ± 0.0011	0.641
		1:3	-0.152 ± 0.0010	0.657	-0.953 ± 0.0021	0.218
		2:1	-0.311 ± 0.0012	0.321	-0.549 ± 0.0010	0.182

The generated regression equation was $y = -0.010x - 0.062$ ($R^2=0.9995$) for Candesartan Cilexetil $y = 0.036x - 0.219$ ($R^2=0.9994$) for Pioglitazone Hydrochloride. Where, 'x' is the

concentration and R is correlation coefficient. The R^2 values indicate that developed method was linear. The proposed method was found to be precise as % R.S.D values for intraday as

well interday precision were satisfactory. The drug at each of the 80%, 100% and 120% levels showed acceptable recoveries. Hence, it can be said that this method was accurate.

Figure 5: Calibration curve for CAN.

The LOD and LOQ were calculated as 0.170 µg/ml and 0.516 µg/ml for Candesartan Cilxetil and 0.207 µg/ml and 0.628 µg/ml for Pioglitazone Hydrochloride respectively. Robustness was performed by small variation in the conditions were found to be unaffected by small variations. Thus it can be said that this

method was robust and Rugged. The result of the analysis of Synthetic Mixture by the developed method was consistent highly reproducible and reliable. Thus the method can be used for the routine analysis of the simultaneous estimation of Candesartan Cilxetil and Pioglitazone Hydrochloride in Synthetic mixture as well as Pharmaceutical dosage form. The validation parameters are summarized in Table 10.

Figure 6: Calibration curve for PIO.

Table 9: Analysis data of commercial formulation *(n=3).

Sr. No	Drug	Formulation (synthetic mixture) (µg/ml)	% Assay* ± SD	USP limit (%)
1	CAN	20	100.33 ± 0.0015	99-101 %
2	PIO	40	100.00 ± 0.0076	98-102 %

Table 10: Summary of validation parameters.

Sr. No.	Parameter	First Order Derivative Method	
		Candesartan Cilxetil	Pioglitazone Hydrochloride
1	Wavelength	327.60 nm	242.00 nm
2	Linearity (µg/ml) (n=6)	10-50 µg/ml	20-100 µg/ml
3	Regression equation	y = -0.010x - 0.062	y = 0.036x - 0.219
4	Correlation coefficient (r ²)	0.9995	0.9994
5	Intraday Precision (% RSD) (n=3)	0.172-0.355	0.165-0.512
6	Interday Precision (% RSD) (n=3)	0.263-0.617	0.249-0.493
7	Accuracy (% Recovery) (n=3)	99.50-100.80	99.27-101.36
8	LOD (µg/ml) (n=10)	0.170	0.207
9	LOQ (µg/ml) (n=10)	0.516	0.628
10	Robustness and Ruggedness (% RSD) (n=3)	0.105-0.946	0.114-0.653
11	Assay	100.33	100.00

Conclusions

It can be concluded from the results that the proposed method was sensitive, accurate, precise and reproducible for the simultaneous determination of Candesartan Cilexetil and Pioglitazone Hydrochloride in Synthetic Mixture. This method was validated as per ICH guideline Q2 (R1). Results suggest that this method can be used for routine estimation.

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